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STRATEGIES FOR IMPROVING CONSTRUCTION SITE PRODUCTIVITY

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Abstract

This study sought to determine the Strategies for Improving Construction Site Productivity. The study was guided by one objectives and corresponding research question. Relevant literatures related to the research question were reviewed. The study adopted survey research design and simple random sampling technique was employed. Forty-five (45) respondents were randomly selected comprising of ten (10) labour workers and five (5) foremen from the three ongoing construction sites. The instrument used for the study was a structured questionnaire and was validated by three experts. The reliability coefficient of the instrument was found to be .775 and hence the instrument was found to be reliable. Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 24 was used to analyse the data that was collected. The data obtained was analysed using Descriptive Statistics of Mean and Standard Deviation. Through the data collected for this study, it was discovered that all the 10 strategies were accepted or agreed upon as strategies for improving construction site. Based on the findings, the result of the research should serve as contribution for future research projects or studies and also help stakeholders in Bauchi, in Nigerian construction industry and others around the world to make sure more strategies are sought for, so as to improve the construction site productivity and also increases the construction industry's contribution to the economy of the country..

Keywords: Strategies, Construction Site, Productivity

Introduction

The overriding purpose of construction industry is to build, and every building is done by workers of different skills onsite/offsite. Productivity improvement in construction projects takes place at the jobsite or at the field of construction. Notwithstanding the relevance of productivity concept in measuring and determining the success of business in an industry, the improvement in the construction industry has been on a backsliding scale when compared to other sectors such as retail, manufacturing etc. (David & Sunday, 2015).

The term “productivity” expresses the relationship between outputs and inputs (Karunarathna & Siriwardana, 2018). Output and input differ from one industry to another. Also, the productivity definition varies when applied to different areas of the same industry. Labour is one of the segments of the construction industry. Therefore, when improving construction productivity, the key is improving the performance of construction workers. In order to enhance the productivity of the workers, critical factors which affect the productivity should be identified Karunarathna and Siriwardana (2018).

The Nigerian construction industry is be-devilled with issues ranging from corruption during the award of contracts, to the total neglect of projects due to cash flow problems. As a result, construction workers have been subjected to a work environment which does not encourage high levels of efficiency. At low levels, Construction Labour Productivity can be dangerous causing social conflicts to a Nation's economy (Shoar & Banaitis, 2019), (Palikhe, Kim, & Kim, 2018). Identification of these factors affecting productivity levels is important, as it will aid site handlers in tackling such problems thereby reducing time and cost overruns (Palikhe et al, 2018), (Seddeeq, Assaf, Abdallah, & Hassanain, 2019). It will also help to improve labour productivity at the sites. The construction industry's productivity is vital considering the enormous effect it has on a Nation's GDP (Hafez, Aziz, Morgan, Abdullah, & Ahmed, 2018et al, 2018). An improved productivity means a rise in GDP.

There are productivity losses in some construction sites due to the non-value adding activities happening at the site as this affects sustainable building (Hafez, et al 2014). Non-value adding activities can be defined as activities that consume time, resources or space but it does not add any value to the project. These non-value activities reduce the workers' productivity because it reduces the final output. Therefore, in order to enhance the worker productivity, they have to be minimized. In this study conducted, authors have categorized the factors affecting worker productivity into management, site and resource management, project characteristics, workforce characteristics and external characteristic factors.

Jarkas and Bitar, (2012) further stated that the root causes of inefficiency in the productivity of workers are poor communication, unskillfulness, and a shortage of construction knowledge. As a matter of fact, supervisors often face difficulties directing job orders and workers frequently struggle to comprehend work instructions.

Construction is a labour-intensive industry in which the skills and experience of workers influence the cost, schedule, and quality of projects significantly (Jarkas & Bitar, 2012). The construction of buildings involves the proper execution of various tasks by many differently skilled workers. The type of construction work performed and the characteristics of the workers involved significantly impact the time required to complete a specific task.

Therefore, since the three most important needs of human being are food, clothes and most importantly shelter; that is why construction industry becomes important to country's economy across the globe. Construction industry is one of the biggest and largest industries in Nigeria, the industry employs good number of Nigerian population and contributes 3.22% of the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) growth in Nigeria in the year 2011 (Corporate Nigeria, 2014). Even though the construction industry is important in the economy of Nigeria, the economic downfall or recession and the constantly changing of leaders in Nigeria has affected the sector where public projects are often left uncompleted or delivered to a poor quality (World Bank, 2004) as cited in (Adagba, Ati & Ibrahim, 2021). Such encounter leads to the termination of ongoing projects or delay to ongoing projects. Such factors are those that affects the productivity in construction industry in a way that labor market sees an unfair wage, negative influencing factors, lack of motivation, lack of training and poor communication etc. the extent of these failures varies within and across countries, driving national and global inequalities (Adagba, Ati & Ibrahim, 2021).

Construction is the way in which something is built or put together. It can also be defined as building of something, especially a large structure such as house, road or bridge (Farlex, 2014). Productivity is the measurement of the rate at which work is carried out. It is the measure of the efficiency of a person, machine, factory, system etc., in converting inputs into useful outputs (Khan, 2017). Construction productivity can be simply illustrated by an association between an input and

output. Productivity is an important factor that affects the overall performance of any construction site, be it small or large project (Santosh & Apte, 2014).

The significant variance in the concept and definition of construction productivity among projects and companies makes creating a comprehensive productivity measurement for construction projects difficult (Lakew, 2017). He further maintains that measuring worker performance by monitoring their worksite activity in real-time is typically time-consuming, costly, and error-prone. Nonetheless, taking into account time and measuring production over time makes it easier to compare productivity and determine its rise or decline.

Any improvement to the construction site productivity will have positive impact on the economic growth of the country (Hafez, et al 2018). Construction industry's productivity is important to any country as it has an effect on the economic growth of a country whatsoever the situation of the industry, negative or positive (Shittu & Shehu, 2010).

In improving productivity, motivation is an important issue that can improve productivity and as such the management need to consider it seriously in order to improve the productivity of a project. The workforce can be motivated through goal setting, incentives, engagement, positive re-enforcement etc (Jarkas & Radosavljevic, 2013) as cited in Lakew 2017. This will boost workers moral hence improving the overall productivity of the industry.

Furthermore, good communication among the project team and the stakeholders is an essential issue that related to project productivity (Jarkas & Radosavljevic, 2013) in Lakew 2017. This is because the interfaces that exist in a project work environment provide the need for each participant to know exactly what his or her roles are in the job. In this way productivity will be improved as there will be no confusion and wasting of time.

Statement of the Problem

The Nigerian construction industry is be-devilled with issues ranging from corruption during the award of contracts, to the total neglect of projects due to cash flow problems thereby affecting productivity (Adagba, Ati & Ibrahim, 2021). Based on the above statement, it is obvious that Nigeria, like many other countries: both developed and developing are faced with the challenges of under performance in the construction industry especially in terms of productivity, which can be seen as time, cost or quality. So many factors such as unsatisfied labor, market, payment, weather and quality of material among others, affects the productivity of projects in Nigeria. Knowing such factors can help with an idea on how to avoid them which will lead to improved productivity.

From the above problem of low productivity in Nigerian Construction Industry which have significant effect on the nation's GDP, it has become imperative to device strategies for improving construction site productivity and that is the gap this study cover.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this research project is to determine the Strategies for Improving Construction Site Productivity.

Research Question

The study was guided by one research question.

1. What are the Strategies for Improving Construction Site Productivity?

Methodology

The research design used in the study was a survey research design. The area of the study was construction sites located within Gubi Campus of Abubakar Tafawa Balewa University Bauchi, Bauchi State. The population of the study constitutes all labour workers and foremen of the construction sites within Gubi Campus of Abubakar Tafawa Balewa University Bauchi. A stratified random sampling technique was employed. Three sites out of four were selected within the area of the case study. Ten labour workers and five foremen were randomly selected from each of the three construction sites, making a total of forty-five (45) respondents. The instrument for data collection for this research was a structured questionnaire developed by the researchers through extensive literature review. The instrument was validated by three lecturers from the Department of Vocational and Technology Education (DVTE) Building Option, Abubakar Tafawa Balewa University Bauchi, Bauchi State. The instrument was administered with the aid of three research assistants from each site selected. The research assistants were educated on the procedure for data collection. Descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation were used to analyze the data. A cut off point 2.99 and below were disagreed and any item with a mean score of 3.00 and above were accepted. The items for response were presented according to the research questions with five points Linkert scale. The ratings are as follows:

Strongly Agreed (SA)	5	point
Agreed (A)	4	point
Undecided (U)	3	point
Disagreed (D)	2	point
Strongly Disagreed (SD)	1	point

Results

Research Question 1: What are the Strategies for Improving Construction Site Productivity?

Table 1: Mean and standard deviation of the respondents on the Strategies for Improving Construction Site Productivity.

S/N	Items	N	X	SD	Remark
1	Paying fair wages to all workers and on time.	45	4.97	.169	Strongly Agreed
2	Proper and effective communication	45	4.77	.490	Strongly Agreed
3	Motivating workers or workforce	45	4.74	.443	Strongly Agreed
4	Providing opportunity for workers training and retraining	45	4.54	.701	Strongly Agreed
5	Early dissemination of information	45	4.54	.780	Strongly Agreed
6	Providing accurate specification	45	4.31	.796	Agreed
7	Eliminating negative influencing factors	45	4.26	.980	Agreed

8	Recruitment of skilled labour	45	4.20	1.052	Agreed
9	Following a adequate sequence of work	45	3.97	.985	Agreed
10	Investment in research and development	45	3.09	1.616	Moderately Agreed

Source: Field Work, 2023.

Table three shows the respondent’s response on how these factors can improve towards achieving higher productivity. The results are in descending order of their relative mean based on the Linkert scale of five (5). This are as follows; Paying fair wages to all workers (4.97) having the highest mean value, proper communication (4.77), motivating workers or workforce (4.74), providing for training and retraining (4.54), early dissemination of information (4.54), providing accurate specification (4.31), eliminating negative influencing factor (4.26), recruitment of skilled labour (4.20), following a adequate sequence of work (3.97), investment in research and development (3.09) having the least ranking mean value.

Finding of the Study

Based on the results obtained the following findings were made by the researcher:

1. In order to achieve or improve productivity in the selected site the following should be employed based on the result collected paying fair wages to all workers, proper communication, motivating workers, providing opportunity for training and retraining, early dissemination of information, providing accurate specification, eliminating negative influencing factors, recruitment of skilled labour and following adequate sequence of work.

Discussion of Findings

In order to improve productivity in the selected construction site the result shows that workers must be adequately paid because when wages are fair it tends to make construction workers to put their effort towards achieving higher productivity. Proper communication must be maintained if higher productivity must be achieved. The workers must be well motivated as there is correlation between worker’s motivation and performance and opportunity should be provided for training and retraining of workers or workforce. Early dissemination of information, providing accurate specification, eliminating negative influencing factors, recruitment of skilled labour and following adequate sequence of work were also recognized as the method of improving construction site productivity within the selected site. As reviewed in the literature workers tend to put more effort when motivated and when paid fair wages. Furthermore, when there is proper communication in given site there will be improved labour productivity. This finding is in agreement with that Lakew (2017) who said all the above-mentioned success strategies must be adhered to if maximum productivity is to be achieved.

Conclusion

In response to the identified factors improving construction site productivity in some selected sites in Gubi campus of ATBU Bauchi, the researcher concludes that these measures to be considered in an attempt to improve the productivity in construction site as such measurement will globally improve the country’s GDP.

Recommendation

The recommendation below could also be used by other companies and nations trying to tackle such factor in construction sites. The finding of this research should serve as up input data for future studies on related topics to this research topic, and to serve as a procedure to stakeholders in construction industry around the globe on eliminating factors that can affect the construction site productivity

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